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Review Article

Nanostructured Lipid Carriers

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ABSTRACT

At present, nanotechnology is widely utilized in drug delivery, facilitating both passive and active targeting through various administration routes. Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) and nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) are the two primary types of lipid-based nanoparticles. Muller developed the NLCs in 1999-2000. NLCs come in three different forms: Imperfect, Amorphous and Multiple. Compared to SLNs, NLCs have a greater drug loading efficiency because their partially crystalline lipid system is created by blending liquid and solid lipids. Various excipients are used in formulating NLCs are commonly used liquid lipids and solid lipids, emulsifying agent, counter ions and surfactant for preparation of NLCs. For thermostable and thermos sensitive medication the high shear homogenization and micro emulsion like various methods for fabrication of NLCs have been described in this review. Evaluation of NLCs includes particle size determination, zeta potential, entrapment efficiency test, NLCs morphology, polydispersity index, stability test, structural analysis. NLCs have numerous pharmaceutical applications like inhalational, parenteral, topical, oral, ocular, brain and other.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, nanotechnology is extensively used in drug delivery, allowing for both passive and active targeting through different administration routes. Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) and nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) are two main kinds of lipid-based nanoparticles. SLNs were created to address drawbacks of other carriers like emulsions, liposomes, and polymeric nanoparticles. They offer advantages such as a

favourable release profile and targeted drug delivery, along with excellent physical stability.

In the next generation of lipid nanoparticles, NLCs are modified SLNs that enhance stability and loading capacity. Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) are a newer type of lipid nanoparticles designed to address the issues of the first generation, known as SLNs. NLCs have become a promising carrier system for delivering medicines

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through methods like oral, injection, eye, lung, skin, and through the skin. NLCs are a combination of solid and liquid lipids, forming a less ordered lipid core. [1, 3]

History –

Muller developed the NLC carrier in 1999/2000. It took 5 years to launch the first two products, Nanorepair Q10 cream and Nanorepair Q10 serum, in Munich/Germany in 2005. The third product, Nanolipid CRL Restore, was launched within half a year. This makes NLC one of the nanocarriers with the shortest time from invention to market introduction. In 12 years, more than thirty products are now available commercially. [2]

Advantages and disadvantages of Nanostructured Lipid Carriers – [3]

Advantages	Disadvantages
Increased drug capacity for certain medication.	Toxic effects linked to the type and amount of lipid used.
Less water in the dispersion.	Skin irritation and sensitization caused by surfactants.
Stop or reduce the leaking of the drug when stored.	Lipid stability.
Control and targeted drug release.	The use and effectiveness of lipid-based systems for delivering protein, peptide drugs, and gene therapies are still to be fully explored.
Practicability of loading both lipophilic and hydrophilic drugs.	Commonly used liquid lipids and solid lipids for preparation of NLCs.

Use of biocompatible and biodegradable lipids.	Excipients used in formulating NLC.
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Types of NLCs:

In simple terms, there are three types of Nanostructure Lipid Carriers (NLCs) based on how they're made and what lipids (fats) are used in their structure. The way these tiny carriers are put together and the ingredients used determine these categories. [4]

1. Imperfect type
2. Amorphous type
3. Multiple type

Imperfect type:

In simpler terms, this type of Nanostructure Lipid Carriers (NLCs) is made by using different types of fats with varying characteristics, like different lengths and levels of saturation in their carbon chains. Mixing these diverse fats creates a structure where the arrangement is not perfect, making it a bit disordered. This disorder allows the carrier to hold more medication, and it's less likely to expel the drug during storage compared to using just one type of fat.

Amorphous type:

In simpler terms, this type of Nanostructure Lipid Carriers (NLCs) creates a structure without a specific pattern, which helps to carry a lot of medication. They achieve this by making the lipid structure solid but not in an organized way, creating what is called an amorphous matrix. Using specific ingredients like medium chain Triglycerides, Hydroxyoctacosanylhydroxystearate, or Isopropylmyristate with a solid lipid can achieve this. Techniques like Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) and differential scanning calorimetry are used to confirm the solid state of the lipids and their transition temperatures, respectively.

Multiple type:

In simpler terms, this type of Nanostructure Lipid Carriers (NLCs) has a solid lipid structure that

contains tiny droplets of liquid oil where the medication dissolves really well. This setup increases the amount of medication that can be held. Moreover, it allows for controlled release of

the drug and minimizes the chances of drug leakage (which is good for stability), because the small oil droplets are surrounded and held in place by the solid lipid structure.

Figure 1 Importance of NLCs

Excipients used in formulating NLCs –

Figure 2 Excipients use in formulation of NLCs

Commonly used liquid lipids and solid lipids for preparation of NLCs: [4]

Component	Name	Purpose
	Oleic acid	Improving the Oral Bioavailability of Simvastatin and Carbamazepine. Delivering Spironolactone Topically for the treatment of Acne Vulgaris.
	Caprylic/Capric triglycerides	Improving the Oral Bioavailability of Thymoquinone and Vinpocetine.
	α-tocopherol/ Vitamin E	Enhancing in Vitro Anti-Breast Cancer activities of Quercetin.
	Black cumin oil	Synergistic Inhibition of Reactive Free

Liquid lipids		Radicals with Marigold/Carrot Extract.
	Soy bean oil	Delivering Itraconazole through pulmonary Route.
	Caraway essential oil	Speeding Up Healing of Infected Excision Wounds.
	Olive oil	Creating Oleuropein-Loaded Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLCs) with optimal physicochemical stability to Mitigate Residual Surfactant-Induced Cytotoxicity
	Sweet almond oil	Enhancing the protection and stability of Cinnamon Essential Oil-Loaded W3 Nanostructure Lipid Carriers (NLCs)
	Squalene	Delivering Calcipotriol and Methotrexate combination topically. Improving the oral bioavailability of Lovastatin
	Capmul MCM C8	Enhancing the bioavailability and Lymphatic Distribution of Tacrolimus. Achieving Sustained Release of Raloxifene Hydrochloride with improved bioavailability
Solid lipids	Compritol 888 ATO	Enhancing skin permeation of Fluocinolone Acetonide for Psoriasis treatment and formulating Clobetasol Propionate in Topical Gel, improving the oral bioavailability of Fenofibrate.
	Precirol ATO 5	Topical delivery of Dapsone. Enhancing the Wound Healing Efficacy of Recombinant Human Epidermal Growth Factor (rhEGF) in a Porcine Full-Thickness Excisional Wound Model.
	Stearic acid	Topical delivery of Tretinoin. Achieving controlled release and acid protection of Progesterone.
	Glyceryl monostearate	Improving the oral bioavailability of Omega-3 Fatty Acids and Raloxifene.
	Cetyl palmitate	Topical delivery of Coenzyme Q10.

Emulsifying Agent

Poloxomer 407, Tween 20, Twee 40, Tween 80, Polyvinyl alcohol, Trehalose, Sodium deoxycholate, Sodium glycocholate, Sodium oleate, Polyglycerol methyl glucose distearate, Egg lecithin, Soya lecithin, Phosphatidylcholines, Phosphatidylethanolamines, Miranol ultra 32.

Counter-ions:

Sodium hexadecyl phosphate, Monodecyl phosphate, Mono hexadecyl phosphate, Mono octyl phosphate, Dextran sulphate sodium salt, Hydrolysed and Polymerized epoxidised soybean oil.

Surfactant:

The choice of surfactant significantly impacts the quality and efficacy of nanoparticle-based liquid crystallization (NLC), affecting toxicity, stability, and crystallinity. Surfactant systems also affect drug dissolution and permeability. Surfactants are chosen based on route of administration, hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB) value, particle size, and lipid modification. Surface active agents (emulsifiers) help reduce tension between lipid and aqueous phases, ensuring stability. The required HLB (rHLB) is crucial for selecting the right type and amount of surfactant for NLC

formulation, ensuring a stable nano system and small particle size. [3]

Method of preparation for NLCs:

Figure 3 Method of preparation of NLCs

1. High Shear Homogenization -

Certainly, based on the information provided, it seems like the process involves two different approaches depending on the thermal stability of the medications: hot, high-a homogenization

(HPH) for thermostable medications and cold HPH for thermosensitive ones. The following chart represents the key steps involved in the process: [5]

Step	Hot HPH (Thermostable)	Cold HPH (Thermosensitive)
1. Lipid Phase Composition	Liquid and solid lipids	Liquid and solid lipids
2. Aqueous Phase Composition	Hydrophilic and lipophilic emulsifiers, double-distilled water	Hydrophilic and lipophilic emulsifiers, double-distilled water
3. Phase Heating	Independently heated to a high temperature	Independently heated to a high temperature
4. Homogenization	High-shear homogenizer followed by sonication	High-shear homogenizer followed by sonication
5. Result	Tiny and consistent size distribution	Tiny and consistent size distribution

2. Microemulsion –

The described process involves creating Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLCs) through emulsification. Here is a summary of the key steps in a chart format: [5]

Step	Description
1. Emulsion Formation	Combine melting lipids with a hydrophilic aqueous phase containing a co-surfactant and a surfactant.
2. Emulsion Types	Emulsion can be either water-in-oil (w/o) or oil-in-water (o/w) based on the ratios of components utilized.
3. Particle Size Reduction	Thoroughly mix the emulsion to reduce particles to a minuscule size range.
4. Microemulsion Formation	A transparent, thermodynamically stable microemulsion forms.
5. Incorporation into Cold Phase	Spread the microemulsion in a cold hydrophilic phase for further particle size reduction and NLC formation.
6. Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLCs)	The cold hydrophilic phase leads to the creation of Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLCs)
7. Characteristics	Straightforward, affordable, and scalable process. Suitable for medications that are thermolabile.
	Does not require additional energy or equipment for NLC production.

This chart outlines the sequential steps involved in the creation of NLCs using the described emulsification process, along with key characteristics of the approach.

3. The Solvent Injection Technique –

Here's a chart summarizing the key aspects of the "solvent injection method" for the quick production of nanoparticles: [5]

Aspect	Description
1. Method	Solvent Injection Method
2. Lipid Dissolution	Dissolve lipids in a water-miscible solvent
3. Injection Process	Rapid injection into a surfactant aqueous solution using an injection needle.
4. Advantages	Straightforward and quick production. Easy preparation without complex apparatus. Limits heat exposure and avoid shear stress.
5. Drawbacks	Low particle concentration utilization Involves the use of organic solvents.
6. Considerations	Careful consideration needed due to the drawbacks associated with low particle concentration and organic solvents.

4. Phase Inversion –

Here's a chart summarizing the key steps and characteristics of the procedure described for the

production of Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLCs): [5]

Aspect	Description
1. Composition	Medication, lipid, water, and surfactant are gently combined.
2. Heating	The mixture is heated to a temperature higher than the surfactant phase inversion temperature.
3. Surfactant Phase Inversion	Above the inversion temperature, surfactant undergoes dehydration, changing its hydrophilic-lipophilic balance.
4. Emulsion Formation	Each phase's affinity changes, causing the emulsion to invert.
5. Quick Cooling	Rapid cooling (e.g., in an ice bath) makes the surfactant hydrophilic again, allowing NLC development.
6. Benefits	Low energy consumption. Avoids the use of organic solvents.
7. Drawbacks	NLCs may have weak temperature stabilities.

	Multiple temperature cycles may be necessary.
8. Considerations	Careful consideration needed due to the drawbacks associated with temperature stabilities and multiple cycles.

This chart provides a succinct summary of the key steps, benefits, drawbacks, and considerations related to the described procedure for Nanostructured Lipid Carrier (NLC) production.

Here's a chart summarizing the key points regarding the solvent emulsification-evaporation method for the preparation of Solid Lipid Nanoparticles (SLNs) and Nanostructure Lipid Carriers (NLCs): [6]

5. Solvent Emulsification-Evaporation Method -

Aspect	Description
1. Method Type	Solvent Emulsification-Evaporation
2. Solvents Used	Water-immiscible organic solvents (e.g., chloroform, cyclohexane, dichloromethane, toluene)
3. Process Steps	Dissolve medication and lipids in a water-immiscible organic solvent.
	Emulsify the solvent mixture in an aqueous phase.
	Evaporate the organic solvent using a rotary evaporator or mechanical stirring.
	SLNs and NLCs are formed as a result of solvent evaporation followed by lipid precipitation.
4. Example: Rifampicin-Loaded SLNs	Chloroform used to dissolve rifampicin, soy lecithin, and monostearin.
	High-speed homogenization and ultra-sonication in an aqueous phase containing 1.5% polysorbate 80.
	Solvent evaporation achieved through stirring.
5.Example: Cefuroxime Axetil-Loaded SLNs	Dissolved in an organic combination of dichloromethane with chloroform (3:1).
	Added to an aqueous phase (poloxomer 188) while homogenizing at high speed and ultra sonication.
	Solvent extraction using a rotary evaporator under decreased force.
6. Impact of Lipid Concentration	Significant impact on average particle sizes (PSs) generated for SLNs and NLCs.
7. Benefits	Suitable for encapsulating extremely thermolabile pharmaceuticals.
	Prevents exposure of drugs to high temperatures.
	SLNs and NLCs have PSs around 100 nm with narrow size distributions.
8. Drawbacks	Requires the use of hazardous organic solvents.
	Resultant diluted suspension may need further evaporation or ultra-filtration.

9. Commonality with Solvent Emulsification-Diffusion	Both methods use organic solvents, necessitating additional solvent cleanup procedures.
10. Safety Considerations	Risk studies (in vitro and in vivo) necessary to ensure solvent levels below designated thresholds for no side effects.

This chart provides a concise overview of the key steps, examples, benefits, drawbacks, and safety considerations associated with the solvent emulsification-evaporation method for SLNs and NLCs.

6. Membrane Contactor Technique –

Certainly, here's a chart summarizing the key information about the membrane contactor method for lipid nanocarrier preparation: [6]

Aspect	Description
1. Method Type	Membrane Contactor Method
2. Operation	Lipid phase in a pressured tank at a temperature higher than its melting point infiltrates through ceramic membrane holes.
3. Droplet Formation	Tiny droplets created as lipid phase infiltrates through membrane holes under applied pressure.
4. Aqueous Phase Flow	Aqueous phase flows tangentially inside the membrane module, continuously stirred, brushing away formed droplets.
5. Lipid Particle Formation	Lipid particles form when the preparation is cooled to room temperature.
6. Process Parameters Influencing Size	Temperature of lipid and aqueous phases.
	Tangential-flow velocity of the aqueous phase.
	Pressure of the lipid phase.
	Size of the membrane pore.
7. Advantages	Commercial scalability.
	Membrane emulsification technique.
8. Commercial Scalability	One of the advantages of the membrane contactor method.
9. Application	Preparation of lipid nanocarriers.

This chart provides a concise overview of the key aspects of the membrane contactor method for lipid nanocarrier preparation, including the method type, operation, droplet formation, advantages, and key process parameters influencing particle.

7. Emulsification Solvent Diffusion Technique –

Here's a chart summarizing the key information about the solubilization of solid pigments and the production of lipid nanoparticles using partially water-soluble solvents: [7]

Aspect	Description
1. Process Type	Solubilization of Solid Pigments and Lipid Nanoparticle Production
2. Solvents Used	Partially water-soluble solvents such as tetra-butyl alcohol, butyl lactate, isobutyric acid, isovaleric acid, hydrofuran
3. Solvent Saturation	Solvents saturated with water to ensure initial thermodynamic equilibrium
4. Lipid Nanoparticle Formation	Formed in the dispersed phase due to the presence of the organic solvent
5. Water to Emulsion Ratios	Typical ratios of 1:5 or 1:10 for water to emulsion
6. Particle Formation Mechanism	Lipid crystallization induced by internal organic solvent diffusion from the organic phase to the aqueous exterior phase

7. Advantages	Utilizes solvents partially soluble in water.
	Lipid nanoparticles formed in the dispersed phase.
8. Solvents Used in Particle Formation	Hydrofuran used to produce lipid nanoparticles.

8. Supercritical Fluid Technique [SFT] - nanoparticles from emulsions using Supercritical Fluid (SCF) technology, also known as "supercritical fluid extraction of emulsion": [7]

Here's a chart summarizing the key steps and aspects of the method for preparing lipid

Aspect	Description
1. Method Type	Supercritical Fluid Extraction of Emulsion
2. Solution Preparation	Dissolve medication and fatty material in an organic solvent (e.g., chloroform) with an appropriate surfactant. Mix with an aqueous solution.
3. Emulsion Generation	Run the combination through a high-pressure homogenizer to generate an oil-in-water (o/w) emulsion.
4. SCF Introduction	The o/w emulsion is introduced into the extraction column.
5. Counter-Current SCF Flow	Supercritical fluid (SCF) introduced counter-currently at a steady-state rate of flow.
6. Lipid Dispersion Formation	Lipid dispersions of nanoparticles created through the ongoing extraction of solvent.
7. Mechanism of Particle Production	Simultaneous processes of lipid dissolution and supercritical fluid extraction (diffusion) of organic solvent from emulsion.
	Lipid crystallization results from the expansion of the organic phase.
8. Extraction Column Configuration	One end of the extraction column is where the o/w emulsion is inserted, and SCF is introduced at the other end.
9. Operating Conditions	SCF maintained at a steady pressure and temperature, typically introduced at the top of the extraction column.
10. Advantages	Utilizes supercritical fluid technology for lipid nanoparticle production.
	Utilizes supercritical fluid technology for lipid nanoparticle production.
11. Dispersed Phase	Lipid dispersions of nanoparticles are formed through the extraction of solvent.

9. Double Emulsion Technique – the synthesis of Solid Lipid Nanoparticles (SLNs) and Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLCs): [7]

Here's a chart summarizing the key steps and characteristics of the double emulsion method for

Aspects	Description
1. Method Type	Double Emulsion Method for SLN and NLC Synthesis
2. Applicability	Well-suited for hydrophilic peptides and active medicinal components.
3. Initial Emulsion Formation	Drug's aqueous solution emulsified in a melting lipid blend to create primary water-in-oil (W/O) emulsion stabilized with excipients.
4. Double Emulsion Formation	Hydrophilic emulsifier aqueous solution mixed with the primary W/O emulsion to create a double water-in-oil-in-water (W/O/W) emulsion.
5. Agitation and Filtration	Double emulsion is agitated and filtered to separate it.
6. Particle Size	Yields relatively large particles.
7. Advantages	Allows the addition of hydrophilic molecules.

This chart provides a concise overview of the key steps and advantages of the double emulsion method for synthesizing Solid Lipid Nanoparticles (SLNs) and Nanostructured Lipid Carriers

(NLCs), particularly when dealing with Lipid crystallization owing to solidification of hydrophilic peptides and active medicinal emulsion.

Mechanism of particle formation is

Evaluation of Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLC)

Figure 4 Evaluation of NLCs

Particle Size –

Particle size refers to the measure of subdivision of a solid material. It's an essential characteristic that affects many aspects of a product's quality and performance. This measurement is especially important in making various products, including pharmaceuticals. The stability of NLCs is greatly influenced by the particle size and the range of size distribution. Smaller particles with a narrow size distribution tend to be more stable, exhibiting a reduced likelihood of aggregation and physical instability during storage. Several factors affect particle size, including the type and concentration of surfactant, the manufacturing method, and the concentration and ratio of liquid lipids to solid lipids. The size of the particles affects their surface area and hence their solubility and biocompatibility as well as the rate of drug release. The formulation parameters, including the amounts and types of lipids, surfactants, and added drug, play a crucial role in determining the particle size and distribution of NLCs. Diameter of NLCs generally ranges from 10 to 1000 nm. [9, 10]

Zeta Potential –

It is the measure of the electrostatic repulsion or attraction between particles. The surface charge of Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLCs) is determined using zeta potential (ZP). Electrophoretic light scattering (ELS) measures the zeta potential of NLCs. The stability of the colloidal dispersion is indicated by the zeta potential. Higher the electrostatic repulsion between the particles the greater is the stability. If the ZP value is above +20 Mv or below -20 Mv, it indicates that the nanoparticles dispersion has good physical stability. [10, 11]

Entrapment Efficiency Test –

It is used to estimate the efficacy of a nanocarrier to retain the drug or active ingredient, to ensure delivery of an adequate amount of the component to the targeted site. Entrapment efficiency defines the ratio between the weight of entrapped drug and the total weight of drug added to the dispersion. [3, 9]

Actual drug content in nanoparticle

$$EE (\%) = \frac{\text{-----}}{\text{Total drug used in formulation}} \times 100$$

NLCs Morphology –

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) -

It is used to visualize NLCs although it provides surface morphology information. The SEM is an instrument that produces a largely magnified image by using electrons instead of light to form an image. A beam of electrons is produced at the top of the microscope by an electron gun. The electron beam follows a vertical path through the microscope, which is held within a vacuum. [11, 12, 13]

It is an uncomplicated and non-instructive method that can be used as a primary tool to both measure and alter the shape and size of lipid nanoparticles. Images were made using a special microscope i.e. Atomic Force Microscopy that measures how things interact. These experiments happened in the air at room temperature (25°C), with a method where a small amount of the final mixture was put on a small flat surface. After the liquid dried, the microscope was used again at room temperature. [3, 14]

Polydispersity Index –

The polydispersity index indicates the uniformity of particle sizes within the sample population, also known as the heterogeneity index. The polydispersity index (PDI) measured from Dynamic Light Scattering Instrument (DLS). This index is dimensionless. [15, 16]

PDI < 0.05 for highly monodisperse standards.

PDI > 0.7 indicates a very broad particle size distribution in the sample.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) -

It gives high-resolution imaging of NLCs, and provide information about morphology, size, shape of particles. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) is a useful method not just for fully understanding the physical and chemical properties of newly created nanoparticles but also for investigating how nanocomposites impact biological systems.

$$\text{Polydispersity index} = \frac{M_w}{M_n}$$

Where,

M_w = Weight average

M_n = Number average molecular weight

Stability Test –

The encapsulation of chemotherapeutic agents in lipid-based NPs improves their chemical and physical stability. Several factors, including storage temperature and pH, can influence the stability of drug-loaded Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLCs). A stability test was performed using real-time conditions at room temperature (25 ± 2 °C). [17]

Techniques to enhance stability of NLCs -

Lyophilization -

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) -

This is mostly used to prevent Ostwald ripening and to avoid the hydrolysis of moisture-sensitive drugs. If lyophilization is done without using a cryoprotectant, it can cause the aggregation of the lipid particles.

Commonly used cryoprotectant – Sorbitol, Mannitol, Glucose, Lactose, Sucrose, Mannose.

Spray Drying –

It is another option instead of lyophilization, and it's also less expensive. Lipid nanoparticles are made more stable in terms of their physical and chemical properties through a process called spray-drying. Before performing the spray drying of NLCs, it's important to ensure that the melting point of lipids is higher than the boiling point of the liquid used for spraying. This helps prevent the degradation of the lipids.

Addition of Poloxomer –

Poloxomer or Pluronics are a class of water-soluble nonionic triblock copolymers formed by polar (poly ethylene oxide) and non-polar (poly

propylene oxide) blocks. which confer amphiphilic and surface active properties to the polymers. Various grades of poloxamers are employed as stabilizing agents. These are commonly used to improve the stability of gel nanoparticles.

Addition of PEG (Polyethylene glycol) –

Nanoparticles are coated with the substance like Polyethylene glycol.

It gives benefits like –

- Improves dispersibility of colloid.
- Decreases the alteration of lipids and growth of NLCs.
- It enhances blood circulation time.
- Helps with targeted drug delivery by changing the interactions of colloids with the mucosal membrane.
- Provides strong physical stability.

Spectral Analysis –

Figure 6 Spectral Analysis

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) –

Differential Scanning Calorimetry can figure out how NLC (Nanostructured Lipid Carrier) components behave when it comes to heat, like when lipids melt or interact with drugs. The substance was put into an aluminum container

after weighing it at 2-8 milligrams. The temperature of the container was then increased at a rate of 10°C per minute until it reached a temperature between 30 and 300 °C. [9, 11]

X – Ray Diffraction Analysis (XRD) –

X-ray Diffraction assists in understanding the organized structure of lipid components and detecting any alterations in the crystalline form of drugs within Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLCs). [11]

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) –

FTIR spectroscopy is used to analyse chemical bonds and functional groups in NLC components and assess drug-lipid interactions. The samples were put into the sample holder on the device,

pressed using a hydraulic press, and then scanned at a wave number of 400-4000 cm⁻¹. [11]

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) –

NMR (Nuclear Magnetic Resonance) spectroscopy can be applied to examine the interactions between drugs and lipids, as well as evaluate how drug molecules are distributed within the lipid structure. [11]

Applications -

Figure 7 Applications of NLCs

Inhalational –

Using inhaled drugs could be a promising approach to treat various lung-related conditions. Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLC) have been created and have several benefits. For instance, they can be used to deliver drugs to the lower respiratory tract. By reducing the particle size to below 500nm, there is an enhanced deposition in all lung regions because of increased diffusional mobility. A longer residence time in the lung is achieved due to the bioadhesive properties of NLC, attributed to their small particle size and lipophilic character. [18]

Parenteral –

Improved bioavailability, targeting, and enhanced cytotoxicity were achieved through the administration of Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLC) via the parenteral route. NLC is seen as a substitute for liposomes and emulsions because it comes with improved features. These include easy manufacturing, the ability to load a lot of drug, greater flexibility in controlling how the drug is released. This makes it suitable for delivering drugs through the veins with passive targeting ability and easy removal. [18, 19]

Topical –

Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLCs) can increase the apparent solubility of enclosed drugs. This helps in creating a high concentration

gradient on the skin, making it easier for the drug to pass through. The nano-sized particles stick closely to the skin surface and release the drugs in a controlled way. Advantage of NLCs including the inclusion of biologically active and biodegradable lipids. These lipids are less harmful, offering features like adhesiveness, skin hydration, lubrication, smoothness, emollience, improved penetration into the skin, and modified drug release. [19]

Oral –

NLCs have been shown to be advantageous for giving poorly water-soluble drugs with low bioavailability through the mouth. In oral forms, Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLC) offer advantages such as higher drug loading, better drug inclusion, ease of use for patients, high concentration of particles, and a consistency similar to cream. Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLC) are a promising method for delivering drugs that are fat-soluble, have low bioavailability, and are particularly suitable for treating gastrointestinal diseases such as inflammatory bowel diseases. [4, 19, 20]

Ocular –

Delivering drugs to the eyes is challenging because of the unique physical and anatomical features of the eyes, along with various restrictions that need to be overcome to reach specific eye tissues. To overcome these challenges and improve the availability of drugs in eye tissues, NLCs were employed as an innovative method for drug delivery. NLCs provide various benefits such as –

- Enhance ocular bioavailability of drugs.
- Prolong residence time of the encapsulated drugs.
- Transcorneal drug delivery system. [4, 20]

Brain –

The significant benefits of this method of administration include bypassing the initial metabolism by the liver and achieving a quick

onset of action. Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLC), from this generation are seen as a key approach for drug delivery without altering the drug molecule. This is due to their quick absorption by the brain, compatibility with the body, and ability to break down naturally. Colloidal drug delivery systems, such as Solid Lipid Nanoparticles (SLNs) and Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLCs), offer the advantage of prolonging the time drugs stay in the blood vessels of the brain. They also create a gradient that helps drugs move from the blood to the brain tissues. Additionally, they widen tight junctions to facilitate entry through the blood-brain barrier (BBB) and promote the transcytosis of drug-loaded Lipid Nanoparticles (LNPs) through the endothelium layer, further increasing the drug's retention time in the brain capillaries. [4, 19]

Other –

NLCs are not only beneficial for treating normal body functioning but also are applicable for various purposes. Some are as follows – [19]

- Cosmetics
- Chemotherapy
- Nutraceuticals
- In food industry
- Gene therapy.

CONCLUSION –

The application of NLCs is extensively used in drug delivery, allowing for both passive and active targeting through different administration routes. Nanotechnology, either SLN or NLC is an advantage. Following an analysis of the studies detailed in this review, we conclude NLCs are a blend of liquid and solid lipids. Consequently, the structural imperfections in the NLCs are increased, leading to improved drug loading and integration efficiency. The selection of excipients specifically solid lipids, liquid lipids, surfactants, emulsifying agents, and counter ions appears to play a significant role in the interaction mechanisms of nanocarrier. Evaluation are done for confirming a

drug's identity and assessing its quality and purity. They offer advantages such as favorable release profile and targeted drug delivery, along with excellent physical stability. NLCs have emerged as a promising system for drug delivery across various routes, including oral, injectable, ocular, pulmonary and transdermal administration.

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